

Workshop: Collective construction of a course on Peace Engineering syllabus from an interdisciplinary dialogue

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Abstract

Engineering and technology for peace have had little theoretical development despite the existence of multiple initiatives in academic practice and intervention in this area. To contribute to fill this gap, the Research Group on Technologies and Innovation for Community Development (GITIDC in Spanish) has been working on a research project, funded by the German-Colombian Center for Peace (CAPAZ in Spanish), entitled "Engaged Engineering and technologies for peace in Colombia. Reflections, practices and future(s)". For the execution of the project, initially, information was collected from different sources, which included a literature review, three discussions with actors who have been working on the issue of Engineering and Technology for Peace, thirteen interviews with experts in this area and four workshops for the participatory design of a subject on engineering and peace. From the discussions generated by the activities, contributions have been made that are aimed at the conjunction between theory and practice to strengthen the proposals of engineering for peace, elaborating the program of a course on engineering and peace that is being developed as a pilot test at the Universidad Libre - Seccional Cali in Colombia. Additionally, we have thought of strategies to disseminate the results that go beyond the participation in academic events and the writing of articles that synthesize the results, including the design of a set of cards (postcard type) to show each of the experiences interviewed and the elaboration of a web page. In order to make the course known and continue the collective construction of the course, it is proposed to develop a virtual workshop at the international level to nurture the contents of the subject, as well as the structure of the course.

Keywords: Engaged Engineering; Engineering Education; Peace Engineering; Peace Studies.

1 Introduction

In order to talk about Peace Engineering, it is important to revisit the origins and development of engineering as a function of war (Riley, 2008), as well as the alternative proposals and praxis (Ochoa-Duarte, 2024) for the construction of peace for humanity, in general, and for communities historically affected by war, in particular.

Peace engineering and technology have been little theoretical, although there are several initiatives in academic practice and the field is being addressed (Reina-Rozo, 2020; Kleba & Reina-Rozo, 2021). To fill this gap, the Community Development Technologies and Innovations Research Group (GITIDC in Spanish) (Reina-Rozo & Ochoa-Duarte, 2021) worked on the research project "Engaged Engineering and Innovation and Innovation Technologies for Peace in Colombia Reflections, practices and the future" funded by the German-Colombian Peace Center (CAPAZ in the Spanish).

Its objectives are, to describe and expand the field of Engineering and Engineering Education for Peacebuilding in a Latin American scenario; to analyze experiences in Engineering and Technology for Peacebuilding in Colombia; and to propose spaces for training at the institutional level in "Engineering for Peacebuilding" within the framework of the Colombian Network of Engineering and Social Development (ReCIDS in Spanish) (Salcedo, Vega & Reina-Rozo, 2021).

Initially, we collected information from various sources, like a literature review, three discussions with stakeholders who worked on Peace Engineering and Technology, thirteen interviews with experts in the field, and four participatory workshops to create a peace engineering course syllabus (Ochoa-Duarte & León, 2023).

We found discussions from different ideological sides, as well as works that contribute to the construction of peace from practice, taking the definition for granted. The synthesis of the results can be found in the project's website (Ingeniería, Tecnología y Paz, 2023).

From this work, it was determined that the course Peace Engineering and Technology in Colombia is an interdisciplinary course that seeks to discuss the role of science, technology and engineering both in the promotion of conflicts and in the search for peace, in order to contribute to the construction of critical thinking among engineering students and other areas through reflection/action, that is, through reading, writing, group discussion and prototyping of solutions. The objective of the course is to make an introduction to the field of engineering for peace through reflections-actions around the role it has played and should play in Colombia, from a historical point of view, discussing current initiatives and possible future paths.

Table 1 below shows the proposed contents of the course. It is important to mention that this course has a theoretical-practical character that can be observed in the topics covered and in the realization of field work and a prototype.

Table 1. Course schedule.

Week	Topics	Week	Topics
1	What kind of peace are we talking about? Positive peace and negative peace. Presentation of the course program.	9	Engineering and <i>Buen Vivir</i> : other possible engineering. Prototype design.
2	History of engineering and its relation to war. Presentation of the problem bank.	10	Engineering for sovereignty (environmental, social, political, food, technological). Prototype design.
3	Ethics, action without harm and engineering. Problem choice.	11	Social technologies for peace. Prototype testing.
4	Engineering, development and its victims. Field trip.	12	Experiences of peace engineering in the world. Prototype validation.
5	Engineering and social injustice. Rapid prototyping workshop.	13	Peace Engineering experiences in Colombia. Prototype improvement.
6	Engineering and environmental injustice. Understanding of the chosen problem	14	The role of science and technology in peace agreements. Implementation budget.
7	Engineering and social justice. Prototype design.	15	Alternative (Engaged) engineering networks. Social appropriation of technology.
8	Engineering and sustainability. Prototype design.	16	Presentation of prototypes and articles.

A pilot test of this course was conducted within the framework of the Social Projection in Engineering course at the *Universidad Libre - Seccional Cali*, during the second semester of 2023. This first scenario, developed virtually, and lasting 1 hour per week throughout the semester, was supported by a professor who is part of ReCIDS, and allowed his students to make discussions, debates and didactic materials (infographics and videos) to meet the learning objectives of the subject. However, the virtuality and the length of the classes were considered as barriers to the teaching-learning processes. Asking to the students at the end of this course,

they agree that it was successful in terms of discussions and results. In addition, they highlight the importance of addressing these issues of engineering and peace from the early stages of their engineering education.

Nevertheless, this experience allowed the opening of other scenarios such as forums, conversations, public policy discussions and specialized publications in other Colombian universities. Such is the case of the participation as guests of the subject Engineering and Society of the *Universidad del Valle* - Palmira branch, in the *Agenda Regional en Educación para que florezca la Paz* of Universidad de Caldas, in the IV Colombian Meeting of Engineering and Social Development, held in Pereira by the Colombian Network of Engineering and Social Development (ReCIDS in Spanish) (Ochoa-Duarte and León, 2023). In addition, the creation of the subject Engineering and Peace has also been attempted at the *Universidad Nacional de Colombia* - Medellín, through the *Instituto de Educación en Ingeniería* (IEI). However, it has not been possible yet.

Also, we propose a definition of Peace engineering that includes both theoretical references and collected data from different experiences. In this sense, this definition becomes a starting point to strengthen both theory and practice in the field of peace technologies, initially in the Colombian context, but can be used to promote new research in other contexts. In this sense, Peace engineering is the application of science and technology in pursuit of collective well-being, socio-environmental justice and social appropriation of technoscience, contributing to the mitigation of direct, structural and cultural violence through technological co-production with the communities involved, in active learning environments. In addition, we considered strategies for disseminating findings that go beyond attending academic events and writing articles synthesizing the findings, including designing a set of (postcard-style) cards showing each interviewees' experiences and a website (Ingeniería, Tecnología y Paz, 2023).

2 Activities

In order to make the course known and continue the collective construction of the course, it is proposed to develop a virtual workshop at the international level to nurture the contents of the subject, as well as the structure of the course. This workshop is oriented to all the people interested in collaborating with the design of the Engineering for Peace course. In this way it is perfectly aligned with the themes of the conference and allows the creation of collaborative networks to strengthen Engineering for Peace.

On the other hand, it is important to mention that no other workshop or special session with a similar theme was found. This also gives more importance to the proposal to be part of the conference. Additionally, workshop participants are members of GITIDC, have explored the topic, conducted interviews and have written an article in which they propose a definition of Peace Engineering.

The methodology of the workshop will consist of collaborative work that will be conducted online, in which the starting point will be discussion-provoking questions that allow both reflection and proposal. A collaborative work platform will be shared, where the different opinions will be posted, first in a general way and then organized in the form of a tree or mind map,

A similar version of this workshop has been done four times. The first was the construction of the engineering and peace course program itself, which was carried out virtually with experts on the subject. The second was a workshop held within the framework of the *Agenda regional en educación para que florezca la paz*, held at *Universidad de Caldas*, in Manizales. The third, was a virtual class that was given to students of an engineering subject at *Universidad del Valle*, Palmira campus. And the fourth, was a workshop in *Tercer Coloquio Tecnología y Sociedad* organized by ReCIDS at *Universidad Nacional de Colombia - Medellín* (Ochoa-Duarte y León, 2024), which was very similar to this event, in which we worked mixing group work with general discussion, avoiding any group dispersion.

The provocative questions are: What content and methodology should an Engineering for Peace course have, what voices should be in an engineering and peace course, and how are they actively incorporated in the process? And what results would be expected from an engineering and peace course, both in terms of learning outcomes and in terms of academic production and impact on a territory?

3 Expected results

It is expected that at the end of the workshop the participants will recognize the importance of building peace engineering in a collective way, and that through the reflection developed in the workshop, they will begin to encourage this type of engineering in their daily activities.

It is also expected that the course program will be strengthened through the dialogue carried out in the workshop.

Additionally, it is expected that the participants will be aware of the need to strengthen peace engineering and promote experiences that explore this topic in their institutions.

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